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An algorithm for the Brewer spectrophotometer ozone calibration transfer with PHYCS

While there are likely many ways to incorporate PHYCS (Savastiouk et al. 2023) stray light correction into the Brewer calibration process, we propose hereby a simple algorithm for doing so that requires only minimal changes to the existing ozone calibration transfer procedure.

Currently, the ozone calibration transfer is done by analyzing simultaneous direct-sun observations done with the reference Brewer and the Brewer being calibrated. Using the ozone values from the reference, the ozone Extra-Terrestrial Constant (ETC) is calculated for the Brewer being calibrated, "New". This is done for each coincidental observation and then the average of the individual ETC values is used as the new calibrated ETC. Normally, the ozone air mass factor μ is limited to a range of 1.2 to 3.5

This standard ETC process can be written as a function of $r6_{New}$

$$o3ETC(r6_{New}) = \text{average}(r6_{New} - o3_{Reference} * \mu * o3_{AbsorptionNew} * 10)$$

Similarly,

$$so2ETC(r5_{New}) = \text{average}(r5_{New} - o3_{Reference} * o3so2_{AbsorptionNew} * \mu * 10 - so2_{Reference} * so2_{Absorption} * \mu * 10)$$

Or, in case of no so_2 , simply

$$so2ETC(r5_{New}) = \text{average}(r5_{New} - o3_{Reference} * o3so2_{AbsorptionNew} * \mu * 10)$$

In order to incorporate PHYCS, the process of ETC transfer is repeated for a range of PHYCS alpha factors. Analysis of dozens of Brewers shows that the alpha factor ranges at most between 0.001 and 0.01 for all single monochromator Brewers. We also established that a precision of 0.0001 is sufficient for the factor alpha. Using this as a guide, the following procedure leads to establishing both the ETCs and the PHYCS factors at the same time. In this process, a larger air mass factor range, e.g. 1.2 ..4.5, is used.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● for alpha_trial = 0.001 .. 0.01 step 0.0001 do <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ recalculate r6New using alpha_trial ○ transfer o3ETC calibration $o3_etc(alpha_trial) = o3ETC(r6New)$ ○ recalculate o3New using $o3_etc(alpha_trial)$ and r6New ○ calculate o3New deviation from o3Reference as $o3deviation(alpha_trial) = \text{sum}((o3New - o3Reference)^2)$ optionally weighing with standard deviation of DS observations ● endfor ● find the minimum of o3deviation ● o3_etc and alpha_trial corresponding to the minimum are the new calibration constants for ozone o3ETC and alpha and these are used for the rest of the process ● for beta_trial = 0.001 .. 0.005 step 0.0001 do <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ recalculate r5New using beta_trial ○ transfer so2ETC calibration $so2_etc(beta_trial) = so2ETC(r5New)$ ○ recalculate so2New using $so2_etc(beta_trial)$ and r5New ○ calculate so2New deviation from so2Reference, or zero if no so2 is present, as $so2deviation(beta_trial) = \text{sum}((so2New - so2Reference)^2)$ optionally weighing with standard deviation of DS observations ● endfor ● find the minimum of so2deviation ● so2_etc and beta_trial corresponding to the minimum are the new calibration constants so2ETC and beta 	<p>For each value of alpha between 0.001 and 0.01 with an increment of 0.0001, the standard method of ETC transfer is used to establish the best agreement between the reference and the Brewer being calibrated. Then, using this calculated ETC and the alpha parameter, the sum of squares of differences between ozone values from the two Brewers is recorded. This way, for each value of alpha, a value for ETC and a value for the ozone deviation is calculated. The minimum in the curve corresponds to a pair of o3ETC and alpha that minimizes the ozone differences between the reference and the Brewer being calibrated. This pair becomes the new calibration values. Once ozone calibration is done, a similar process leads to so2ETC and beta.</p>
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Experimentally, we found that the deviations of both O₃ and SO₂ as functions of respective PHYCS parameters are smooth curves with a single minimum as shown in the plot below.

Since the curve has only a single minimum, the process of going through values of alpha can be stopped, if done in a monotonic fashion, as soon as the minimum is reached. However, doing the calculations for a range of values around the minimum will provide a way to estimate the effects of uncertainty in alpha on the ETC.

Furthermore, the curves are almost ideal parabolas and can be easily approximated by a quadratic polynomial using only a few points, and then the minimum found using the fit parameters.

To establish uncertainty for alpha and ETC when using this algorithm, a number of well known methods can be employed. For example:

- Repeating process with a randomly selected subsets of data
- Varying the range of air mass factor in the data set or alternatively varying the range of ozone slant density column

References

Savastiouk, V., Diémoz, H., and McElroy, C. T.: A physically based correction for stray light in Brewer spectrophotometer data analysis, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 16, 4785–4806, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-16-4785-2023>, 2023.